

This readme contains the description of the code necessary to generate all figures and tables in the paper "Healthy ageing for all? A health growth incidence curve approach" by Carrieri, V., Jones, A. M., Principe, F. and Speziali, M. M.

The SHARE data are distributed by SHARE-ERIC (Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe – European Research Infrastructure Consortium) to registered users through the SHARE Research Data Center.

Details on how to register and access the SHARE data after completion of the registration are available through the following portal: <https://share-eric.eu/data/data-access>.

In this paper, we use waves 1 and 6 and obtain a dataset at the individual level between 2004 and 2015. Our final sample includes the following countries: Austria, Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Sweden, and Switzerland. Full details about the variables used in the analysis are contained in the paper Data section and Table 1.